

Report on EU open science practices and transfer of knowledge and skills

Report prepared by Biljana Kosanović and Milica Ševkušić

WP2: Developing and Adjusting Guidelines, Policies, and Incentives

A1 Study visit to the Leiden University and University of Udine to transfer know-how regarding on EU open science practices and transfer of know-how regarding the guidelines, mandates, and legislations underpinning open science in research and education

21 August 2018

The European Commission support for the production of this document does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of Contents

Introduction	3
Defining the role of an Open Access / Open Science policy	3
European open science policies.....	4
The foundations of European open science policies (key documents)	4
The existing OA/OS policies in Europe.....	6
Sources of information	6
Types of policies.....	6
Key topics addressed in European Open Access / Open Science policies	11
Lessons learned: Study visits to the University of Leiden and the University of Udine	16
Netherlands.....	16
Italy	19
Serbia's Open Science Platform	21
Implementation challenges in Serbia	22
Conclusion.....	24
References	25
ANNEX 1: PhD theses in Library and Information Science at the University of Belgrade (2013-2017)	30

Introduction

The primary aim of [Work Package 2](#): Developing and adjusting guidelines, policies, and incentives is to develop national and institutional open science policies that will enable efficient open scientific communication and wide dissemination of publicly funded research outputs. In doing this, project partners and the team implementing WP 2 are to rely on a huge body of documents (primarily recommendations and reports) drafted by the European Commission and national bodies in the European Union (EU) countries, as well as on the knowledge exchange achieved during two study visits conducted as part of the BE-OPEN project: the [study visit to the University of Leiden](#) (May 2017) and the study visit to the [University of Udine](#) (September 2017).

The main purpose of this report is to offer a brief analysis of European Open Access (OA) / Open Science (OS) policies and especially the policies of partner universities, with the aim of identifying optimal solutions for Serbian OA/OS policies at various levels. The drafting of the report was undertaken after the first study visit. However, the course of actions undertaken under WP2 had to be changed due to the fact that [in July 2017, the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development \(MESTD\) established an official working group tasked with drafting an open science platform](#) that would apply to the outcomes of projects fully or partly funded by the MESTD. The first draft of the Open Science Platform was prepared in November 2017.

The report will briefly describe the main characteristics and elements of European OA/OS policies, the lessons learned during the study visits and explain the elements of the draft of the Serbian Open Science Platform.

Defining the role of an Open Access / Open Science policy

The main purpose of an OA/OS policy is to ensure Open Access to and the reuse of research outputs, especially those publicly funded. This is normally achieved through mandates – sets of obligations imposed on researchers requiring them to deposit their publications in OA repositories, or to publish in OA journals, to archive their research data and make them publicly available and reusable (if there are no legal limitations), defining technical standards for research infrastructures supporting OS and procedures to achieve OA.

According to the European Commission Recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information C(2012) 4890 final [1] “Open Access policies aim to provide readers with access to peer-reviewed scientific publications and research data free of charge as early as possible in the dissemination process, and enable the use and re-use of scientific research results.” OA/OS policies should take into account the copyright-related issues and they should apply to all publicly funded

research. Open Access to research data should help avoid research duplication and enhance the quality of research.

The requirements that national and sub-national OA policies should meet are defined in the same document. An OA policy should define:

- concrete objectives and indicators to measure progress;
- implementation plans, including the allocation of responsibilities;
- associated financial planning.

These issues are further elaborated in the OSPP-REC: Open Science Policy Platform Recommendations (2018) [2]. The document defines a set of recommended actions and measures that need to be taken in the years to come (especially through FP9 – Horizon Europe) in order to make OS possible. Stress is laid on the interoperability of research infrastructures and standardization (persistent identifiers, metadata formats, etc.) and the need to integrate the culture of OS into research practices, education, training and research evaluation. It is very specific about what must be ensured/achieved at various levels and it provides a framework for future OS policies in Europe.

European open science policies

The foundations of European open science policies (key documents)

The key EU documents related to OA/OS that have served as the sources for the existing policies in European countries include [3]:

- [A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth COM\(2012\) 392 final](#) [4], where an “optimal circulation, access to and transfer of scientific knowledge including via digital ERA” is defined as one of the ERA priorities;
- [Towards better access to scientific information: Boosting the benefits of public investments in research COM\(2012\) 401 final](#), which highlights that OA can foster economic growth and address societal challenges and “sets out measures to ensure that the results of Europe’s publicly-funded research are fully accessible for researchers, businesses and citizens” [5];
- [Commission Recommendation of 17.7.2012 on Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information C\(2012\) 4890 final](#), which deals with policies and practices on open access to scientific publications and research data, and preservation and use of scientific information. It seeks to coordinate national policies [1];
- [Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, COM\(2011\) 808 final](#) [6];
- [Commission Recommendation \(EU\) 2018/790 of 25 April 2018 on Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information](#) [7], which is the revised version of Recommendation C(2012) 4890 and it addresses recent developments, such as research data management (and the concept

of FAIR¹ data), the increased capacity of data analytics, text and data mining (TDM), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC),² skills and competences for open science, incentives and reward systems for researchers;

- [OSPP-REC: Open Science Policy Platform Recommendations](#), 22 April 2018 [2];
- [Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Laying down Its Rules for Participation and Dissemination – COM\(2018\) 435 Final](#) [12], which defined OS as the first pillar of the new EU framework programme.

Other important EU documents include:

- [European Open Science Agenda](#) (2016) [13];
- [Digital Single Market Strategy COM\(2015\) 192 Final](#) [14], where the access to, the circulation and the transfer of scientific knowledge are discussed in the context of increasing innovation, jobs and economic growth in the EU.

Documents of the European University Association (EUA)³ are also highly relevant for university policies:

- [Recommendations from the EUA Working Group on Open Access adopted by the EUA Council on 26th of March 2008](#) [16];
- [EUA's Open Access Checklist for Universities: A Practical Guide on Implementation](#) (2015) [17];
- [EUA Roadmap on Open Access to Research Publications](#) (2016) [18];
- [Towards Full Open Access in 2020: aims and recommendations for university leaders and National Rectors' Conferences](#) (2017) [19].

The document *Open Science and Its Role in Universities: A Roadmap for Cultural Change* [11], issued by the League of European Research Universities sets out recommendations about what universities can and should do in the transition to OS.

¹ In order to be put in service of OS, research data must be easy to find, identify and contextualize. In 2016, the FAIR guiding principles for research data were published and they have since become the staple of all policy recommendations. FAIR is the acronym from Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. In brief, research data must be supplied with rich metadata and persistent identifiers, deposited on a searchable platform that have open protocols for access and sharing and assigned a license that clearly defines usage rights [8].

² The EOSC will be developed as a data infrastructure to support and develop open science and open innovation in Europe. It will federate existing resources across national data centres, European e-infrastructures and research infrastructures and provide common services to all users [9–11].

³ In 2015, EUA has set up an Expert Group on Science 2.0/Open Science to support universities in the implementation of institutional policies on Open Access to research publications and data, text and data mining and big data, as well as a wide range of issues related to the EU Digital Agenda [15].

The existing OA/OS policies in Europe

Sources of information

The main source of information on the existing OA/OS policies is the [ROARMAP: Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies](#).⁴ It currently lists more than 900 Open Access policies, 83 (57 in Europe) of which are funder policies and 716 are institutional OA policies. Although the registry was significantly improved during the Pasteur4OA project [20, p. 13-16], it should be borne in mind that it is still incomplete and some records are not up-to-date. This is confirmed by the 2016-2017 EUA Institutional Survey: only about 60% of institutions with an OA policy have registered them in ROARMAP [21, p. 8].

According to [ROARMAP](#), more than 40% (422) of the registered policies mandate depositing peer-reviewed manuscripts, while depositing books and book chapters is mandated in nearly 25% of the registered policies. Less than 10% (80) of the registered policies mandate open data.⁵

The outputs of the project Pasteur4OA include a body of useful resources available from the project's website (under [Advocacy resources](#)). Along with case studies on national, institutional and funder policies, there are two sets of policy guidelines: *Toolkit for research performing organizations* and *Toolkit for research funders*. These resources have been especially useful for the work within the BE-OPEN WP 2.

Valuable information on OA/OS policies is provided in the implementation reports of the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation

- Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information in Europe: Report on the Implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 Final (2015) [3];
- Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information in Europe Report on the Implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 Final (2018) [22];

and EUA Open Science surveys:

- [Open Access in European Universities: Results from the 2015/2016 EUA Institutional Survey](#) [23];
- [Open Access in European Universities: Results from the 2016/2017 EUA Institutional Survey](#) [21].

Types of policies

Generally speaking, OA/OS policies may be roughly classified as national, funder and institutional policies. In practice, this classification is not so strict, as some funder policies may actually serve as national policies. The typology of documents that serve as 'policies' is diversified: OA-related provisions and policy elements may be included in various types of documents, such as laws, codes of ethics, national plans, strategies, guidelines, roadmaps, etc. In terms of coverage, it is possible to

⁴ A detailed report on OA policies relying on the data provided by ROARMAP was prepared as part of the Pasteur4OA project [20].

⁵ Only two OA policies from Serbia are registered and these are actually journal policies incorrectly classified as funder/institutional policies.

distinguish between policies on publications and data policies. In practice, this is not so simple, as publications and data may be addressed in the same document, or research data may be covered in documents dealing with government data, etc. As far as OA mandates are concerned, we may speak of 'hard' and 'soft' policies. The former involve mandatory OA and contain terms such as 'must' and 'should', whereas the latter merely recommend and/or encourage OA.

EU policy – Horizon 2020

The Horizon 2020 OA policy is funder policy where OA to peer-reviewed scientific publications is mandatory. The main elements of the Horizon 2020 OA policy are [24]:

1. OA is mandatory for peer-reviewed publications;
2. The policy is a Green OA mandate (repositories) – publishing in subscription-based journals and depositing an author's copy in an OA repository;
3. For Gold OA, the payments from grants for OA journal publication fees are allowed, where they are foreseen by the project budget;
4. OA is not explicitly mandated for monographs;
5. The policy is definite about Open Research Data (ORD), announcing an Open Data Pilot – OA to data is mandatory since 2017.

The next EU Framework Program, Horizon Europe (2021-2027), will place an even stronger focus on OS. Open Science will be the first pillar of the programme [25]. In this context, the 2018 Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP) [2], which defines the framework for the long-term development of OS, will play a major role. The document includes a set of recommendations related to the eight priorities identified from the European Open Science Agenda:

- Rewards and Incentives
- Research Indicators and Next-Generation Metrics
- Future of Scholarly Communication
- European Open Science Cloud
- FAIR Data
- Research Integrity
- Skills and Education
- Citizen Science.

The recommendations lay stress on interoperability and standardization.

OA policies to publications in European countries: National, funder and institutional

According to the most recent report on the implementation of the EC Recommendation C(2012) 4890 [22],⁶ the majority of the countries have adopted, are implementing or are currently discussing national policies for OA to publications. Most national policies/strategies were adopted recently

⁶ The report is a summary of the data collected in a survey in the autumn of 2017. It is based solely on self-reporting and covers EU Member Countries and six Western Balkan countries.

(2015–2017), with the earliest dating to 2009. Several countries have set the policy goal – to ensure OA to all publicly funded scientific publications until a specific year – e.g. 2024, in Norway, Switzerland, the Netherlands. Still, in one-third of the countries (11), the public funding means that the effects of policies were not properly monitored.

Research data policies

At the European level, the issue of ORD is addressed through the Research Data Pilot in Horizon 2020. The Pilot seeks to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data created and collected in Horizon 2020 projects.

A recent survey conducted by SPARC [26] has shown that, in some European countries, the progress in open research data is slower than that in open government data. In some countries (Austria, France), the acts on the reuse of public sector data also apply to research data. In January 2018, 11 of the 28 European Union member states and two non-EU members (Norway and Switzerland) covered by the survey had national research data policies. The majority of the policies were funder policies. Other types of policies included national plans or roadmaps, codes of ethics, white papers, and even laws. Most policies were adopted after 2009. In seven out of the 13 countries with policies in place, research data were covered in the same policy as OA to publications. The same number of countries had the so-called “hard” policies, whereas in the remaining six countries, research data policies were ‘soft’. Many policies specified situations where data should not be shared (ethical, commercial, or security reasons) [26].

The SPARC survey draws attention to the fact that the existing research data policies do not conform to a uniform model or concept because of the great diversity of research data (depending on the research discipline), different needs of research institutions (in terms of size and scope of data) and different standards that apply to metadata describing research data in various disciplines [26], p. 4].

According to the 2018 Report on the Implementation of Commission Recommendation [22], only a dozen countries provide national funding for Research Data Management (RDM), though in many countries the costs related to open research data are considered eligible. In more than half countries at least some institutions have included Data Management Plans (DPM) and ORD in their policies and strategies, but the FAIR principles are still rarely included as a concept. In many countries, RDM is only applied in EU funded projects. In half the countries, funding for RDM is available at the institutional level, while for the rest funding is primarily provided from EU funds.

The 2016-2017 EUA Institutional Survey [21] offers an insight into the situation at universities. Only about 19% of the surveyed universities had an institutional research data management policy and nearly 20% of the institutions had only informal guidelines in place. This means that about 60% of the institutions had neither a research data policy, nor RDM guidelines. It is interesting that the majority of them (nearly 65%) indicated the absence of national guidelines as the main reason for the absence of institutional guidelines on RDM.

Table 1. Open Access policies to publications and research data

Member state / country	Government policy / strategy (publications)	Document / comment	Year adopted	Preferred oa model	Institutional policies	Funder OA policies to publications	National research data policies	Document / comment	Year adopted	Funder and institutional data policies
<i>EU</i>										
AUSTRIA	Yes, in discussion	Austrian Science Fund (FWF) Roadmap of Open Science policies (major national funder); since 2004 recommended; since 2008 mandated		Green	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, in discussion	Austrian Science Fund (FWF) Roadmap of Open Science policies and a pilot programme on Open Data since 2014		Some
BELGIUM	Yes	Brussels Declaration on Open Access	2012	Both	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, adopted	Code of Ethics for Scientific Research in Belgium	2009	Some
BULGARIA	Yes, in discussion	National Strategy for Development of Scientific Research in the Republic of Bulgaria 2017–2030 stipulates a national policy		Green	Some institutions	None	No	A team working on OS and ORD policy		Some
CROATIA	Yes, in discussion	OA policy mentioned in the Research and Innovation Infrastructures Roadmap 2014–2020		Both	Some institutions	None	No	Mentioned in the Research and Innovation Infrastructures Roadmap 2014–2020		None
CYPRUS	Yes, adopted	National policy of Cyprus regarding OA to scientific information	2016	Both	None	Some funders	Yes, adopted	National policy of Cyprus regarding OA to scientific information	2016	None
CZECH REPUBLIC	Yes, in discussion	OA policy mentioned in the National Strategy on open access of the Czech Republic to Scientific Information for years 2017–2020		Both	Some institutions	None	Yes, in discussion	National Strategy on Open Access To Scientific Information (2017–2020)	2017	Some
DENMARK	Yes, implemented	Denmark – A Nation of Solutions, Enhanced cooperation and improved frameworks for innovation in enterprises. Ministry of Science, Innovation and Higher Education” National Open Access Strategy since 2014	2012 2014	Green	Some institutions	All national funders	Yes, adopted	National plan: Denmark – a nation of solutions, Enhanced cooperation and improved frameworks for innovation in enterprises. Ministry of Science, Innovation and Higher Education”	2015	Some
ESTONIA	Yes, implemented	Open Science in Estonia: Open Science Expert Group of the Estonian Research Council, Principles and Recommendations for Developing National Policy	2016	Both	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, in discussion	Open Science in Estonia : Open Science Expert Group of the Estonian Research Council, Principles and Recommendations for Developing National Policy		Some
FINLAND	Yes, in discussion	Open Science and Research Initiative (ATT) for the promotion of research information availability and open science platform for the years 2014-2017		Both	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, implemented*	National plan: Open Science and Research Roadmap 2014–2017	2014	Some
FRANCE	Yes, adopted	Loi n°2016U1321 pour une République numérique	2016	Both	Some institutions	None	Yes, adopted	Loi n°2016U1321 pour une République numérique	2016	Some
GERMANY	Yes, implemented	Open Access Strategy "Open Access in Germany	2016	Both	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, in discussion	DFG – Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data (major national funder) since 2010		Some
Greece	Yes, in discussion			Green	Some institutions	None	Yes, in discussion			None
HUNGARY	No	The major national funder (Hungarian Scientific Research Fund) mandates OA		Both	Some institutions	All national funders	Yes, in discussion	A committee, since autumn 2017		None
ITALY	Yes, in discussion			Both	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, in discussion			None
IRELAND	Yes, adopted	National Principles for Open Access Policy Statement	2012	Green	Some institutions	All national funders	Yes, in discussion			None

Member state / country	Government policy / strategy (publications)	Document / comment	Year adopted	Preferred oa model	Institutional policies	Funder OA policies to publications	National research data policies	Document / comment	Year adopted	Funder and institutional data policies
LATVIA	No			Both	Some institutions	None	No			Some
LITHUANIA	Yes, adopted	Law on Higher Education and Research of the Republic of Lithuania	2009	Green	Some institutions	All national funders	Yes, adopted	Research Council of Lithuania's "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Data"	2016	Some
LUXEMBOURG	Yes, implemented	FNR Open Access Policy	2017	Both	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, in discussion			Some
MALTA	No			Green	No	None	No			None
NETHERLANDS	Yes, implemented	National Plan Open Science	2017	Gold	All institutions	All national funders	Yes, adopted	National Plan Open Science	2017	All
POLAND	Yes, adopted	Directions of the development of open access to research publications and research results in Poland	2015	Green	Some institutions	None	No	Only briefly mentioned in the national OA policy		None
PORTUGAL	Yes, implemented	Policy on management and sharing of data and other results arising from FCTU funded research	2014	Green	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, adopted	Policy on management and sharing of data and other results arising from FCTU funded research	2014	Some
ROMANIA	Yes, adopted	National Strategy for Research and Innovation 2014-2020	2015	Green	Some institutions	None	Yes, adopted	National Strategy for Research and Innovation 2014-2020	2015	All
SLOVAKIA	Yes, in discussion			Both	None	None	Yes, in discussion			None
SLOVENIA	Yes, adopted	National strategy of open access to scientific publications and research data in Slovenia 2015-2020	2015	Green	None	All national funders	Yes, adopted	Data pilot planned Action plan on OA		None
SPAIN	Yes, implemented	Science, Technology and Innovation Act	2011	Green	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, in discussion	Discussions at ministry level		Some
SWEDEN	Yes, adopted	Proposal for National Guidelines for open access to Scientific Information	2010	Gold	All institutions	Some funders	Yes, in discussion	Some work in progress, Swedish Research Council and the National Library, Proposal for National Guidelines for open access to Scientific Information		Some
UNITED KINGDOM	Yes, implemented	RCUK Policy on Open Access	2013	Gold	Some institutions	Some funders	Yes, adopted	Concordat on Open Research Data	2015/2016	Some
NON-EU										
NORWAY	Yes, in discussion			Both	Some institutions	All national funders	Yes, in discussion			Some
SWITZERLAND	Yes, adopted	Swiss National Strategy on Open Access	2017	Both	Some institutions	Some funders	No	Programme SUC P-2 "Scientific information: access, processing and safeguarding" since 2014		All
TURKEY	Yes, in discussion	National open access Committee established		Green	Some institutions	None	Yes, in discussion			Some

Sources: [22], [26], <https://www.openaire.eu>)

Key topics addressed in European Open Access / Open Science policies

The insight into the existing European policies reveals a diversified landscape (in some countries, OA is merely recommended and not mandated; various content types are covered by OA mandates; deposit times are different, etc.). Nevertheless, practically all of the existing policies address, in greater or lesser detail, the following topics:

- Relationship between public funding and public access;
- Relationship between OA/OS and research integrity;
- Mandating OA and monitoring the effectiveness of OA mandates;
- Reshaping research evaluation to include OA;
- Open publishing system
- Copyright.

Relationship between public funding and public access

One of the key principles of Open Access and Open Science is that publicly funded research should be publicly available, so as to enable academia, professional communities, industry, the education sector, etc. to benefit from (publicly funded) research results. This principle is highlighted in European OA and OS policies and it should also be highlighted at the national and institutional levels. This is very important because the idea of OA/OS is often subject to prejudiced and superficial interpretations, according to which OA is:

- identified solely with publishing in APC-charging journals;
- identified solely with public access (Gratis OA) with undefined reuse rights;
- seen merely as a way to increase the visibility and citation counts of publications without fully understanding the component of social responsibility.

Although they may help motivate some researchers to embrace OA/OS, superficial interpretations often act as a hindrance to the development of OA/OS on a wider scale. When devising a policy, it is crucial to interpret OA/OS as an expression of the social accountability of science.

Publicly available publications, data and other research outputs are especially important in the context of citizen science, the involvement of non-professional scientists in research, which is one of the eight priorities of OS [11], p. 20–21].

Relationship between OA/OS and research integrity

OA/OS is often seen as a way to mitigate the so-called reproducibility crisis and increase the reliability and integrity of research. Not only that OA may help discover errors and detect misconduct, but the awareness that publications and data will be publicly available and possibly subject to additional scrutiny may help preclude misconduct. OA/OS policies may increase the efficiency of other research-related policies, rules and regulations.

The relationship between open data / transparent procedures and research integrity is mentioned in [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) adopted by the ALLEA – All European Academies [27]. In the recommendations to universities set out in LERU Advice Paper No. 24, the connection between OS and research integrity is even more explicitly highlighted. According to the document, universities should, “develop awareness amongst the research community of how Open Science can ensure the highest standards of research” [11], p. 20].

Mandating OA and monitoring the effectiveness of OA mandates

As demonstrated by OA implementation surveys,⁷ the problem of recruiting full-text content for institutional repositories is present (metadata without full text). It is necessary to devise a policy to ensure that both metadata and full text are deposited. Rather low (full-text) deposit rates suggest that the metadata are mostly deposited due to the technical support of responsible bodies (imported from other systems) and they reflect the lack of awareness and interest on the part of researchers.

A number of studies have demonstrated that Green OA mandates lead to a more efficient recruiting of OA content to repositories, i.e. to higher deposit rates [20, p. 23–44; 28, 29]. In a study using data from the Spanish policy effectiveness database, MELIBEA, it has been found that the following policy conditions may increase the effectiveness of an OA policy: (i) requiring immediate deposit (ii) requiring deposit for performance evaluation and (iii) allowing waiver for the OA requirement but not allowing any waivers for the deposit requirement [29].

Deposit rates for monographs are rather low in EU countries. This is due to the publishing model, where monographs are published by commercial publishers. Furthermore, monographs are often not mentioned in OA policies, i.e. they are often not covered by OA mandates.

Although tools and indicators for monitoring OA/OS compliance ([MELIBEA score](#), [JISC Monitor](#), [Danish Open Access Indicator](#), [EC Open Science Monitor](#)) are being developed, the lack of reliable input data for the analysis is still a major obstacle. The 2018 Report on the implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 draws attention to the lack of open and reliable datasets of publicly funded research outputs that include systematic funding references and the outputs’ OA status. The monitoring of OA compliance is still predominantly manual. In some countries, it is not clear who is responsible for compliance monitoring and there are no dedicated human or financial resources for this. Another major obstacle is the lack of standardized monitoring procedures across institutions, as well as the lack of reliable quantitative indicators [22], p. 11].

⁷ See above under [OA policies to publications in European countries: national, funder and institutional](#)

Reshaping evaluation to include OA/OS

Evaluation systems based on bibliometric data have been widely criticized [30–32] over the past decade as:

- unsuitable to measure the impact of individual articles;
- not equally relevant for physical sciences and social sciences and humanities and unable to capture the specific qualities of the latter;
- fostering misconduct due to pressures caused by the publish or perish approach;
- relying on data behind a paywall (produced and sold by profit-oriented companies).

Several altmetric (article-level metrics) projects ([Impact Story](#), [PlumX](#), [Altmetric](#), [Dimensions metrics](#)) seek to measure the impact of research outputs beyond journal citations. It should be pointed out that these new tools have certain limitations [33]:

- as the underlying data are usually not available, we never really know what they track and what they fail to capture;
- the proliferation of alternative metrics involves a risk of “gamification”, i.e. their true purpose may be neglected and the quest for high scores may become a purpose in itself [34];
- they track publicly available sources but they are not open: some of the projects are commercial and there is a risk that someday they may be entirely behind the paywall.

An overview and analysis of the currently available and used metrics is provided in the report *Next-generation metrics: responsible metrics and evaluation for open science* [35], issued by the EU Expert Group on Altmetrics.

European policies recommend the introduction of OA/OP-related evaluation criteria, e.g. introducing incentives for depositing publications and, especially, data, or rewarding the readiness to publish. Such measures could motivate researchers to adopt OA/OS practices, leading to increased deposit rates or a stronger preference for OA journals. Currently, OS policies rarely mention specific incentives. However, there is a considerable ongoing work in this area in the EU, e.g. within the Working Group on Rewards, Expert Group on Indicators and Expert Group on Altmetrics [35]. The document *Evaluation of research careers fully acknowledging Open Science practices* [36], drafted by the European Commission’s Working Group on Rewards, is particularly interesting, as it proposes a comprehensive approach to researcher assessment using the Open Science Career Assessment Matrix (OS-CAM). The matrix relies on the evaluation of actions, practices, interactions and involvement in OS.

Open publishing system

Although in May 2016, the European Council of Ministers set the goal of making immediate open access to scientific peer-reviewed publications the default by 2020, current policies in Europe do not seem to be sufficient to ensure that the goal is delivered. The subscription-based publishing model is

still dominant and the research evaluation systems that reward publishing in journals with a high impact factor help large commercial publishers maintain their position. Sustainability remains a major issue for OA journals and platforms [37].

Apart from the Gold and Hybrid OA models based on APCs paid by authors and their institutions, other OA publishing models are being developed:⁸

- no-APC Gold OA, also called Platinum or Diamond OA (free both to readers and the authors), where publication costs are covered by publishers from their own funds or through grants, sponsorship or public subsidies. The online version of the journal is free for readers, whereas the print version, if any, may be sold.
- Freemium model ([e.g. OpenEdition](#)), where a publishing platform is maintained through membership fees by member institutions; the content is available in multiple formats to all readers but only some of them (usually HTML) are freely available to readers, whereas the others are available to member institutions and through purchase; the authors are not charged;
- The [Open Library of Humanities model](#), where the platform is maintained through membership fees paid by libraries; neither authors, nor readers are charged; the platform hosts journals by various publishers, as well as one multidisciplinary megajournal practicing open peer review);
- The [SCOAP³](#) (Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics) model, where the costs of OA in key journals in the field of High-Energy Physics are paid by the SCOAP³ (the partnership of libraries, funding agencies, research centres and NGOs). In turn, publishers reduce subscription fees to all customers, who can redirect these funds to SCOAP³. Authors retain copyright; articles are published under the CC BY license and TDM is allowed.

According to the study *Towards a Competitive and Sustainable OA Market in Europe*, there are indications that the role of journals might be taken by open publishing platforms, including a wider range of research outputs, such as research data and software [37], p. 26]. In 2017, the European Commission made a step in this direction by deciding to set up a publishing platform for scientific articles. The Platform is intended to provide an OA publishing venue free of charge to the beneficiaries of Horizon 2020. It will manage the entire publication process, from submission to publication, as well as post-publication curation and preservation. It will also implement an open peer-review system and host pre-prints. Published articles and hosted pre-prints will be openly available to all researchers and citizens. A call for tender concerns was published late in March 2018.

As the innovative OA publishing models often involve redirecting public funds towards specific platforms or consortia, the future OA/OS policies will certainly have to address more specifically the issue of eligible publishing venues.

⁸ An analysis of various OA publishing models can be found in [38].

Copyright

A major obstacle to OA/OS is the fact that for many scientific publications the right holders are not the authors but academic publishers. This is due to the common practice of transferring all rights, including copyright (and sometimes granting exclusive rights), to publishers. The publishers' standard copyright transfer agreements usually do not allow authors to deposit the published versions of their articles in OA repositories. If it is allowed to deposit the submitted or accepted version of the manuscript, this is only after an embargo period. The publishers make profit by selling the results of publicly funded research. Many authors are not aware of the terms of the agreements (do not read / do not understand / are not interested).

In order to ensure that authors retain sufficient rights to enable OA to their articles, tools and instruments have been developed, to cite merely some of them:

- [SPARC Author Addendum](#) is a legal tool that amends the publisher's agreement, allowing authors to keep the rights to reproduce and disseminate their articles for non-commercial purposes;
- [UK Scholarly Communications Licence](#) is a tool that seeks to enable authors to retain copyright for the academic, while granting the publisher a non-exclusive licence to publish; the purpose of the license is to enable re-use of the published content, especially for teaching [11, p. 8].

Nevertheless, a far-reaching solution to this problem cannot be achieved through policy only. In some countries, efforts are made to facilitate OA through the modification of the copyright law. In the Netherlands, an amendment was added to the Dutch copyright law in 2015 to ensure that authors retain the right to enable public access to the text of their publication within 'a reasonable period' [39]. In Germany, the authors of scientific articles have the right to 'secondary publication' as of 2014; the authors of articles stemming from research with 50% or greater public funding are allowed to make their journal articles accessible to the public. In December 2016, the German Copyright Code was amended to facilitate reuse for education and research purposes and enable text and data mining. The new draft of the Irish Copyright and other Intellectual Property Law Provisions Bill seeks to facilitate non-commercial research and text and data mining [22, p. 19]. In Switzerland, researchers are encouraged to retain their copyright and has also been suggested that the national Copyright Act should be modified so as to enable secondary publication.

According to the 2018 Report on the Implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890, Portugal has proposed that EU copyright regulations be changed by introducing "an EU-wide provision for publicly funded researchers to retain a non-transferable and exclusive right to self-archive and make available the author's final version of their publications [...] in an open access repository with no embargo periods to access whatsoever" [22, p. 20].

Lessons learned: Study visits to the University of Leiden and the University of Udine

The Netherlands and Italy have different approaches to OA/OS and their implementation. The Dutch approach may be described as top-down: the provisions of the National Plan are consistently transferred downward, to lower organization levels. Gold OA is mandated. The goals ('milestones') of the process and the roles of various stakeholders are clearly defined and the process is well-coordinated. Monitoring mechanisms are in place. Great attention is paid to innovative approaches to research evaluation and publishing models. On the other hand, the Italian national OA mandate is defined in a law that is not directly associated with research. Green OA is mandated. Infrastructure is available, as well as support for the implementation, but due to the lack of clear goals, coordination and awareness at high levels of decision-making, the results are not satisfactory. Local publishers are rather conservative and generally do not support OA.

Netherlands

In the Netherlands, the awareness of OA/OS is widespread at all levels – from the government to individual institutions. The principles of the Dutch national OA policy are expressed in a [letter by State Secretary Sander Dekker to the Dutch House of Representatives](#) in November 2013 [40]. The principal aim of the policy is to switch entirely to the Gold OA route until 2024 (60% of publications should be OA in five years). As the policy promotes immediate access to publications, even hybrid OA is preferred to Green OA, which often involves long embargo periods.

Open science was a top priority during the Netherlands EU presidency. One of the results of the Dutch presidency is the [Amsterdam Call for Action](#) (2016), which recommends to EU Member States to adopt National Plans for Open Science [41]. The Call for Action led to [EU Council conclusions](#) according to which publicly-funded scientific publications must be accessible to all by 2020 and the optimal reuse of research data should be ensured [42].

In February 2017 the [National Plan Open Science](#) [43] was adopted in the Netherlands. The purpose of the Plan, which is sponsored by the government's Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, is to enable a transition towards an open science system. The National Plan Open Science concentrates on three key areas:

1. promoting OA to scientific publications;
2. promoting optimal use and reuse of research data;
3. adapting evaluation and award systems to bring them into line with the objectives of OS (reward systems)

Open education, the use of open source software, or citizen science, are not discussed in the Plan. The Plan provides a framework for institutional policies.

The implementation of the Plan is well-coordinated and supported by a whole network of bodies and institutions. All universities have their repositories, usually connected to or integrated with CRIS (Current Research Information System) systems, which provide data for research evaluation. The content from the repositories of Dutch universities,⁹ Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW), Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), and research institutes is harvested by the national portal [NARCIS](#).¹⁰ The universities of applied sciences maintain their own portal, the [HBO-kennisbank](#), which is also harvested by NARCIS [44].

As far as research data are concerned, the National Coordination Point has been established with a mission to prepare, facilitate and monitor the development and implementation of the Research Data Management Policy for scientific research in the Netherlands. According to its vision, in 2020, research data management should be an “integral part of the way of thinking about and practising research and education in Dutch research universities and research institutions” [45]. Currently, the Dutch data policy is not ‘hard’ and it addresses the need to devise appropriate evaluation and monitoring mechanisms and incentives and rewards for OS efforts [26, p. 14]. Nevertheless, since 1 October 2016, a data management policy is implemented in all projects funded by NWO. According to it, data must comply with FAIR principles [46]. The national e-infrastructure for research and education is coordinated by SURF, a collaborative ICT organisation, which enables access, transport, long-term storage and analysis of research data. SURF is also involved in the EOSC pilot (a H2020 project) [43].

Libraries play a major role in the OS ecosystem in the Netherlands by providing support to researchers in depositing their publications. University libraries (accompanied with IT staff and policy departments) provide guidance and support to researchers in data management. Libraries organize training courses on research data management and RDM plans, especially for PhD students. An OA working group is active under the auspices of the UKB consortium (the consortium of university libraries and the National Library of the Netherlands). It keeps track of developments in the field of Open Access relevant for university libraries and makes recommendations to the UKB about participation in various OA initiatives. The Working Group takes care that the role of Green OA is not underestimated [47].

Since the Gold OA route is the preferred road to OA in the Netherlands, the deals with publishers are very important [48]. The negotiations with the publishers are managed in cooperation with the Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU) and [UKB](#) with the aim of achieving the best possible conditions for Gold and Hybrid OA [44].

⁹ All universities in the Netherlands have had their repositories since 2005. Until 2014 the Green OA route was preferred.

¹⁰ NARCIS has been developed by Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS, an institute of KNAW funded by NWO), in close cooperation with universities and other research institutions.

Several innovative projects in the area of OA publishing have been initiated in the Netherlands:

- [OAPEN](#), a platform for hosting freely accessible academic books, mainly in the area of humanities and social sciences. It was developed between 2008 and 2010 as part of a project seeking to ensure sustainable publication model for academic books in humanities and social sciences. It is now maintained by the OAPEN Foundation.¹¹ OAPEN also maintains the Directory of Open Access Books – DOAB, a discovery service for OA books hosted on various platforms.
- [Fair Open Access](#), a concept promoted by the Fair OA Alliance, a group of scholars and librarians seeking to “return control of the publication process to the scholarly community” primarily by flipping journals from subscription to OA [50]. The members of the alliance include the [Open Library of Humanities](#), an international non-profit organization seeking to develop a fair and sustainable model of OA publishing in which APCs are not paid by authors [51].

Great attention is also paid to responsible metrics and considerable research in this area is being done at the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), University of Leiden. The CWTS, which is famous for research in bibliometrics, compiles the Leiden Ranking, an annual global university ranking based on bibliometric data [52, 53]. At the same time, director of the CWTS, Paul Wouters, is one of the initiators of the [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#), which puts forward ten principles for the proper use of scientometric indicators in research evaluations, and responsible metrics are one of the primary research focuses of the CWTS [31].

Lessons learned:

- Top-down approach, a ‘hard’ OA mandate and monitoring mechanisms yield results. The same approach could work in Serbia.
- The Dutch model (as a whole) could not work in ‘poor’ countries because it requires considerable resources.
- Libraries and librarians must adopt new roles and skills in order to support OA/OS.
- Serbian publishers and researchers in humanities should get informed about (and involved in) innovative OA publishing models.
- It is necessary to raise the awareness of research evaluation bodies in Serbia of the development related to next-generation metrics, responsible metrics and innovative research evaluation indicators.

¹¹ Established by the University of Amsterdam, the University of Leiden, the University Library of Utrecht University, the Netherlands Academy of Sciences, the National Library of the Netherlands and Amsterdam University Press [49].

Italy

In Italy, provisions related to OA to publications are included in the law on cultural heritage *Urgent Provisions for the Protection, Enhancement and Promotion of Cultural Assets, Activities and Tourism* (13G00135) (G.U No. 186 of 09.08.2013). According to the law, research outputs funded at least 50% with public funds and published in scholarly journals should be OA [54]. However, the implementation of the provisions is not satisfactory due to poor coordination and the lack of awareness. Furthermore, the heritage law is not the most logical document to stipulate OA, as the main public funder and the body responsible for research is the Ministry of Education, Universities and Research (MIUR). The attitude of Italian publishers towards OA is another obstacle. Only a few university presses are OA, whereas some are overtly against OA. Local journal publishers, usually small, are also against OA (especially in humanities).

In 2006, the Conference of Italian Universities Rectors (CRUI) established a Working Group on OA as part of the CRUI Library Committee. The Working Group is mainly focused on drafting guidelines, e.g. *Guidelines on depositing Doctoral Dissertations in open access repositories* (2007), *Recommendations on OA and Research Evaluation* (2009); *Guidelines for OA Journals* (2009); *Guidelines for Institutional Repositories* (2009); *Guidelines on the creation and management of OA metadata* (2012); *Guidelines on Drafting Institutional Policies and Mandates for Publications and Data Sets* (2013).

There is no national OA/OS policy in Italy. Twenty-three universities have adopted institutional policies (66 have not). In only 17 universities, OA is mandatory [54]. Since 2016, OA for PhD theses is mandatory at 38 universities.

The implementation of institutional policies is supported by dedicated OA offices established by universities. Apart from checking and validating deposits, research offices are involved in negotiations with publishers and they organize courses on OA/OS and copyright for PhD students. Nevertheless, deposit rates are still rather low and many records in repositories contain only metadata [55].

Advantages:

- The activities of the consortium (CINECA) providing IT solutions and support to research institutions
- a standardized software platform (IRIS) developed by the consortium
- The existence of dedicated OA offices

Weaknesses:

- The lack of coordination
- No national policy
- Relatively weak mandates

The repository infrastructure is developed ([133 Italian repositories registered in OpenDOAR](#)). The vast majority of university repositories (62) use IRIS (Institutional Research Information System) as the software platform; it was developed by the CINECA, a not-for-profit consortium (67 Italian universities, nine research institutions and MIUR). IRIS rests on DSpace-CRIS, which means that it integrates a repository and a CRIS. The system is supplied with tools facilitating metadata import (from various databases, e.g. CrossRef, Scopus, Web of Science, etc.). Repository content is harvested by the national aggregator [PLEIADI](#) [54].

The [OA policy of the University of Udine](#) (adopted in 2015) is a ‘soft’ OA policy, which means that it is not mandatory. It covers journal articles, books and book chapters, conference objects and PhD theses. On the other hand, the institutional repository is used in the evaluation of research outputs at the university level (only deposited items, no matter whether closed or OA, are taken into consideration in the evaluation procedure).

There is no national research data policy in Italy, but announcements and reports of the MIUR suggest that some work is in progress. The Conference of Rectors of Italian Universities, CRUI, has a Working Group on Open Access (since 2006). A small working group (IT experts, librarians and research administrators from five Italian universities) has produced templates for institutional research data policy and implementation guidelines. Nevertheless, a lack of coordination is apparent [26], p. 17–18].

Lessons learned:

- Where there is a lack of coordination, a ‘hard’ policy and a top-down approach (a national policy) may yield better results.
- The establishment of dedicated OA offices is a good idea, under the condition that competent and trained staff is available.
- A standardized software platform developed and offered to institutions could help establish a national repository infrastructure. Therefore, the team of the University of Novi Sad has undertaken to adjust DSpace CRIS to the needs of Serbian universities.

Serbia's Open Science Platform

At the time of the study visits, in Serbia, OA was mandated only for PhD theses. Apart from the OA mandate for Horizon 2020 projects, there were no other OA/OS policies (e.g. institutional) in Serbia, at the time.¹²

In [July 2017, a working group was established by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development \(MESTD\)](#) with the task of preparing a funder OS policy. The Ministry is the main public funder of research in Serbia. The success of the OA mandate for PhD theses in Serbia, introduced by the MESTD, has demonstrated that in a country where the majority of research institutions are rather small and difficult to coordinate, and the repository infrastructure is poor, a top-down approach to OA/OS policies is the only feasible model.

The initial draft for the policy was provided by the Pasteur4OA team. It covered OA to publications. The draft was further developed taking into account the analysis of policies in EU countries, the information obtained during the study visits, and the local context. Research data were included in the draft, along with publications. A part of the working group suggested that the policy should also address open peer review and open methodologies. However, during the discussion, this idea was rejected as 'premature'. It was agreed that the title of the policy should be 'Open Science Platform'. In brief, the main elements of the policy are:

1. Open Access is mandatory ('hard' policy) for all publications resulting from publicly funded research, including journal articles, monographs, book chapters, conference objects, PhD theses (already mandated since 2014).
2. The policy is a Green OA mandate (repositories) – publishing in subscription-based journals and depositing an author's copy in an OA repository;
3. The allowed embargo periods are somewhat longer than in the Horizon 2020 OA mandate;
4. For Gold OA, the payments for OA journal publication fees are considered eligible if foreseen by the project budget;
5. OA for research data is not mandated; it is merely recommended ('soft' policy); the Platform specifies situations where data should not be shared;
6. The Platform provides a framework for defining institutional policies;
7. It does not mention evaluation but it may be expected that institutional policies will seek to establish a link between the OA content available in institutional repositories and promotion procedures, especially at universities.

The funder policy is intended to serve as an umbrella document. The draft sets out merely the basic requirements, including the technical requirements for repositories, and all other details (depositing procedures, responsibilities for training, administration, monitoring the efficiency of OA policies, etc.) will be addressed in institutional policies.

¹² <https://web.archive.org/web/20170223053051/https://www.openaire.eu/oa-serbia>

It was particularly important to specify the minimum technical requirements for infrastructure in this umbrella document. Unlike most European countries, Serbia does not have a developed repository infrastructure, due to which most researchers are not familiar with the operation of repositories, the importance OAI-PMH and metadata quality, OA licenses, etc. They often do not understand the difference between uploading content to institutional websites and depositing it in repositories. In order to avoid non-standard and non-interoperable solutions, which may also involve the wasting of public funds, this draft OS policy explicitly defines the basic technical requirements. It is also important to ensure a certain level of quality control regarding metadata integrity by including relevant provisions in institutional policies.

Although the FAIR principles are not explicitly mentioned in the Platform draft, their essence is contained in its provisions.

Implementation challenges in Serbia

The major challenge to the implementation of OA/OS principles in Serbia is the underdeveloped repository infrastructure [56]. A national network of institutional repositories and/or a national repository aggregator are topics yet to be discussed.

Publishers' embargo policies may also be a major challenge for Green OA mandates in Serbia. A significant number of Serbian researchers publish with publishers imposing long embargo periods (e.g. Elsevier, 24 and even 48 months). The current evaluation system in Serbia basically relies on the impact factor and it may be difficult to persuade researchers to take into account Green OA-related criteria when selecting a journal to publish their research.

In EU countries, librarians have had a crucial role in implementing OA/OS policies. Librarians are major advocates of OA/OS; they are involved in training programmes aimed at instructing researchers to deposit publications and data; they also control metadata quality and policy compliance [21, p. 18–19]. In order to support the implementation of OA/OS policies competently and efficiently, librarians need to adopt and develop new skills, which are outlined in the competency profiles defined by the Task Force on Librarians' Competencies in Support of E-Research and Scholarly Communication, jointly launched in June 2016 by the [The Association of Research Libraries](#) (ARL), the [Canadian Association of Research Libraries](#) (CARL), the [Association of European Research Libraries](#) (LIBER), and [COAR](#) (Confederation of Open Access Repositories). The Task Force has so far devised [Librarians' Competencies for Research Data Management](#) and [Librarians' Competencies for Scholarly Communication and Open Access](#).

There are indications that Serbian librarians might not be able to provide adequate support to the implementation of OA/OS policies. The [survey on OS attitudes among Serbian scholars](#) [57] conducted within the framework of the BE-OPEN project suggests that the role of librarians in Serbian research institutions is not so strong as it is at European universities (nearly 50% of the respondents said that they never asked for librarian's help when seeking information). One of the

reasons for this may be a bad practice, not uncommon in Serbian research institutions, of appointing inadequately trained persons as librarians. Some research institutions do not have librarians at all. Another problem is a lack of interest on the part of librarians for adopting new skills.

In Serbia, Library and Information Science (LIS) education for academic and research librarians is provided at the University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philology, at the bachelor's, master's and PhD levels. However the study programmes are largely focused on traditional library skills and do not include knowledge and skills related to OA/OS, i.e. they are not in line with the above-mentioned competency profiles. The list of the titles of LIS PhD theses defended at the Faculty of Philology in Belgrade between 2013 and autumn 2017 (Annex 1) reveals a complete lack of interest in OA/OS-related topics and, in this respect, it accurately reflects the character of the curriculum. Out of 27 theses, only one deals with metadata in digital libraries. Others are mostly focused on the history of libraries, individual collections, bibliographies, library management and text processing. It is therefore, reasonable to assume that university-trained librarians in Serbia are not familiar with OA/OS concepts and practices and would need extensive training in these areas before getting involved in OA/OS policy implementation.

Continuing Professional Development programmes for librarians¹³ have offered a wider range of topics – including multimedia, copyright, metadata, Open Linked Data, and even OA, though mainly through very general courses on information literacy or OA to heritage, in the context of *Europeana*. Topics related to Open Science have not been covered.

The policy seeks to facilitate Gold OA publishing by recognizing publication fees as eligible costs. This has not been the case so far. Institutional accounting offices still lack clear instructions how to treat these costs. It is not uncommon that authors cover the cost of Gold OA from their private funds. Nevertheless, establishing OA funds at the national level does not seem to be a realistic option due to the lack of money.

Most research monographs published in Serbia are publicly funded and are usually not used commercially. In most cases, they are published by academic and research institutions and their publication is often subsidized by the MESTD. These books are usually available on institutional websites and it is reasonable to expect that they will be readily deposited in repositories and that deposit rates for monographs in Serbia will be higher than in the EU. However, over the past year or two, it has been possible to observe a negative trend: the institutions that partner with international publishers (usually CEEOL) are required to stop open access to their books, if they wish to distribute them through these publishers. In order to prevent this, it is necessary to include provisions related to the OA mandate in contracts for subsidies.

There are more than 400 OA journals in Serbia and the majority of them do not charge APCs, as they rely on (mostly public) subsidies. Their general OA orientation is not disputable [58]. However, only a part of them comply with the [New Principles on Open Access Publisher Services](#) [59], defined by

¹³ E.g. https://www.nb.rs/view_file.php?file_id=5111, https://www.nb.rs/view_file.php?file_id=4195

Science Europe in the document Science Europe Principles on Open Access to Research Publications (2015), and the [requirements set by DOAJ in 2014](#). Another major problem is the financial sustainability of these journals. In this respect, initiatives seeking to devise sustainable OA publishing models, such as FAIR OA, Open Library of Humanities and OA university presses, are highly relevant in the local context.

Enabling OA to research data will be particularly difficult to coordinate. Currently, researchers who would like to make their data open do not know where to ask for advice. The lack of local expertise is considerable.

Conclusion

The landscape of European OA/OS policies is diversified. It is apparent that it would be impossible to apply a uniform model in all countries and institutions. Policies are often determined by available resources and the local context. With the rise of internationally coordinated infrastructures, such as OpenAIRE and the future EOSC, local policies must meet some internationally agreed requirements. A national policy should provide a flexible framework for defining policies at lower levels. As the discussions concerning research infrastructures in Europe and especially the EOSC are developing, it will certainly be necessary to revise, repeatedly, national, funder and institutional policies in order to address these developments.

The development of OA in Serbia has been imbalanced. On the one hand, there is an underdeveloped repository infrastructure (though with some positive recent developments), whereas on the other, there is the fully implemented OA mandate for PhD theses. There are also a significant number of APC-free OA journals. Once adopted, the Serbian Open Science Platform is expected to foster the development of the local repository infrastructure. The draft fully complies with recommendations provided at the European level and offers a flexible framework for defining institutional policies.

References

1. Commission Recommendation of 17.7.2012 on access to and preservation of scientific information C(2012) 4890 final. 2012. European Commission. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/recommendation-access-and-preservation-scientific-information_en.pdf. Accessed 14 June 2018.
2. *OSPP-REC: Open Science Policy Platform Recommendations*. 2018. European Commission. Available from: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5b05b687-907e-11e8-8bc1-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>. Accessed 14 June 2018.
3. Tarazona Rua, Maria, Daniel Spichtinger, Celina Ramjoue, and Jean-François Dechamp, ed. 2015. *Access to and preservation of scientific information in Europe: report on the implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 final*. Luxembourg: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. Available from: <http://bookshop.europa.eu/uri?target=EUB:NOTICE:KIO215993:EN:HTML>. Accessed 14 June 2018.
4. *A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions*. 2012. COM(2012) 392 final. Brussels: European Commission. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/reinforced-european-research-area-partnership-excellence-and-growth>. Accessed 14 June 2018.
5. *Towards better access to scientific information: Boosting the benefits of public investments in research: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions*. 2012. COM(2012) 401 final. Brussels: European Commission. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/era-communication-towards-better-access-to-scientific-information_en.pdf. Accessed 14 June 2018.
6. Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation COM(2011) 808 final: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. 2011. European Commission. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0808>. Accessed 14 June 2018.
7. Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 of 25 April 2018 on access to and preservation of scientific information. 2018. European Commission. Available from: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2018/790/oj>. Accessed 14 June 2018.
8. The FAIR Data Principles. 2014. *FORCE11*. September 3. Available from: <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>. Accessed 16 July 2018.
9. European Cloud Initiative – Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe COM/2016/0178 final: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. 2016. European Commission. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0178>. Accessed 16 July 2018.
10. *EOSC Declaration: European Open Science Cloud. New Research & Innovation Opportunities*. 2017. Brussels. Available from:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/eosc_declaration.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none.

Accessed 16 July 2018.

11. *Open Science and its role in universities: a roadmap for cultural change*. 2018. Advice Paper No. 24. League of European Research Universities. Available from: <https://www.leru.org/files/LERU-AP24-Open-Science-full-paper.pdf>. Accessed 28 July 2018.
12. Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination – COM(2018) 435 final. European Commission. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-horizon-europe-regulation_en.pdf. Accessed 28 July 2018.
13. Draft European Open Science Agenda. 2016. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/draft_european_open_science_agenda.pdf. Accessed 28 July 2018.
14. Digital single market. 2018. Text. *European Commission*. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/priorities/digital-single-market_en. Accessed 21 August 2018.
15. Science 2.0/Open Science. 2018. *European University Association*. <http://www.eua.be/policy-representation/research-innovation-policy/science-2-0-open-science>. Accessed 12 August 2018.
16. Recommendations from the EUA Working Group on Open Access adopted by the EUA Council on 26th of March 2008 (University of Barcelona, Spain). 2008. European University Association, Working Group on Open Access. Available from: http://www.eua.be/Libraries/research/Recommendations_Open_Access_adopted_by_the_EUA_Council_on_26th_of_March_2008_final_1.pdf?sfvrsn=0. Accessed 12 August 2018.
17. EUA's Open Access checklist for universities: A practical guide on implementation. 2015. European University Association. Available from: http://www.eua.be/Libraries/publications-homepage-list/Open_access_report_v3.pdf. Accessed 12 August 2018.
18. EUA Roadmap on Open Science to research publications. 2016. European University Association. Available from: <http://eua.be/Libraries/publications-homepage-list/eua-roadmap-on-open-access-to-research-publications.pdf>. Accessed 12 August 2018.
19. Towards full Open Access in 2020: Aims and recommendations for university leaders and National Rectors' Conferences. 2017. European University Association. Available from: <http://www.eua.be/Libraries/publications-homepage-list/towards-full-open-access-in-2020-aims-and-recommendations-for-university-leaders-and-national-rectors-conferences>. Accessed 12 August 2018.
20. Swan, Alma, Yassine Gargouri, Megan Hunt, and Stevan Harnad. 2015. Open Access Policy: Numbers, Analysis, Effectiveness. *Pasteur4OA Work Package 3 report: Open Access policies*. Available from: <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/375854/>. Accessed 12 August 2018.
21. Morais, Rita, and Lidia Borrell-Damian. 2018. *Open Access in European universities: results from the 2016/2017 EUA institutional survey*. Brussels: European University Association. Available from: <http://eua.be/Libraries/publications-homepage-list/open-access-2016-2017-eua-survey-results.pdf>. Accessed 12 August 2018.

22. Tsoukala, Victoria, and Maarja Adoojan, ed. 2018. *Access to and preservation of scientific information in Europe report on the implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 final*. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. <https://doi.org/10.2777/642887>.
23. Morais, Rita, Julian Bauer, and Lidia Borrell-Damian. 2017. *Open Access in European universities: results from the 2015/2016 EUA institutional survey*. Brussels: European University Association. Available from: <http://www.eua.be/Libraries/publications-homepage-list/oa-survey-2015-2016-results.pdf?sfvrsn=4>. Accessed 12 August 2018.
24. *Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020. Version 3.2*. 2018. Brussels: European Commission, Directorate – General for Research & Innovation. Available from: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf. Accessed 15 August 2018.
25. EU budget for the future: Horizon Europe. 2018. European Commission. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/budget-may2018-research-innovation_en.pdf. Accessed 15 August 2018.
26. *An Analysis of Open Data and Open Science Policies in Europe, v2.1*. 2018. SPARC Europe. Available from: <https://sparceurope.org/download/2285/>. Accessed 15 August 2018.
27. *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*. 2017. Revised Edition. Berlin: ALLEA – All European Academies. Available from: <https://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>. Accessed 15 August 2018.
28. Gargouri, Yassine, Chawki Hajjem, Vincent Larivière, Yves Gingras, Les Carr, Tim Brody, and Stevan Harnad. 2010. Self-Selected or Mandated, Open Access Increases Citation Impact for Higher Quality Research. *PLOS ONE* 5: e13636. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0013636>.
29. Vincent-Lamarre, Philippe, Jade Boivin, Yassine Gargouri, Vincent Lariviere, and Stevan Harnad. 2014. Estimating Open Access Mandate Effectiveness: The MELIBEA Score. *arXiv:1410.2926 [cs]*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1410.2926>.
30. San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). 2012. Available from: <https://sfdora.org/>. Accessed 15 August 2018.
31. Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics. 2015. Available from: <http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>. Accessed 15 August 2018.
32. Lariviere, Vincent, and Cassidy R. Sugimoto. 2018. The Journal Impact Factor: A brief history, critique, and discussion of adverse effects. *arXiv*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1801.08992>.
33. Haustein, Stefanie. 2016. Grand challenges in altmetrics: heterogeneity, data quality and dependencies. *Scientometrics* 108: 413–423. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-1910-9>.
34. Hammarfelt, Björn, Sarah de Rijcke, and Alex Rushforth. 2016. Quantified academic selves: The gamification of research through social networking services. *Information Research* 21. Available from: <http://www.informationr.net/ir/21-2/SM1.html>. Accessed 15 August 2018.
35. Expert Group on Altmetrics. 2017. *Next-generation metrics : responsible metrics and evaluation for open science*. Available from: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b858d952-0a19-11e7-8a35-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>. Accessed 15 August 2018.

36. *Evaluation of research careers fully acknowledging Open Science practices : rewards, incentives and/or recognition for researchers practicing Open Science*. 2017. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. <http://doi.org/10.2777/75255>.
37. Johnson, Rob, Mattia Fosci, Andrea Chiarelli, Stephen Pinfield, and Michael Jubb. 2017. *Towards a Competitive and Sustainable OA Market in Europe – A Study of the Open Access Market and Policy Environment*. OpenAIRE, Research Consulting. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.401029>.
38. Lara Speicher, Lorenzo Armando, Margo Bargheer, Martin Paul Eve, Sven Fund, Delfim Leão, Max Mosterd, Frances Pinter, and Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou. 2018. OPERAS Open Access Business Models: White Paper. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1323707>.
39. Copyright. 2018. *open access.nl*. <http://www.openaccess.nl/en/tools/copyright>. Accessed 20 August 2018.
40. Dekker, Sander. 2014. Open Access to publications: Parliamentary document. *Government of the Netherlands*. January 21. Available from: <https://www.government.nl/documents/parliamentary-documents/2014/01/21/open-access-to-publications>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
41. Amsterdam Call for Action on Open Science. 2016. Rapport. *Government of the Netherlands*. April 4. Available from: <https://www.government.nl/documents/reports/2016/04/04/amsterdam-call-for-action-on-open-science>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
42. Council Conclusions on the transition towards an Open Science System 9526/16. 2016. Council of the European Union. Available from: <http://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9526-2016-INIT/en/pdf>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
43. National Plan Open Science. 2017. Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, Netherlands. Available from: https://www.openscience.nl/binaries/content/assets/subsites-evenementen/open-science/national_plan_open_science_the_netherlands_february_2017_en_.pdf. Accessed 17 August 2018.
44. De Leeuwe, Just, and Elly Dijk. 2018. Open Science in the Netherlands. *OpenAIRE*. Available from: <https://www.openaire.eu/oa-in-the-netherlands-2>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
45. About LCRDM. 2018. *National Coordination Point Research Data Management*. Available from: <https://www.surf.nl/en/lcrdm/about-lcrdm>. Accessed 21 August 2018.
46. What does academia want? 2018. *open access.nl*. <http://www.openaccess.nl/en/what-does-academia-want>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
47. Open access. 2018. *UKB*. <https://www.ukb.nl/open-access>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
48. Publisher deals. 2018. *open access.nl*. Accessed 17 August 2018.
49. Organisation. 2018. *OAPEN*. <http://www.oapen.org/content/organisation>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
50. Fair Open Access. 2018. *Fair Open Access Alliance*. <https://www.fairopenaccess.org/>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
51. About. 2018. *Open Library of Humanities*. <https://www.openlibhums.org/site/about/>. Accessed 17 August 2018.
52. CWTS Leiden Ranking. 2018. *CWTS Leiden Ranking*. <http://www.leidenranking.com>. Accessed 20 August 2018.
53. Waltman, Ludo, Paul Wouters, and Nees Jan Van Eck. 2018. Ten principles for the responsible use of university rankings. *CWTS: meaningful metrics*. <https://www.cwts.nl:443/blog?article=n-r2q274>. Accessed 20 August 2018.

54. Gargiulo, Paola. 2016. OA in Italy. *OpenAIRE*. September 20. <https://www.openaire.eu/oa-italy>. Accessed 20 August 2018.
55. Comparing the alignment of University Open Access Policies in Italy. 2016. *Authorea*. https://authorea.com/users/87802/articles/101108/_show_article. Accessed 5 December 2017.
56. Milosavljević, Branko. 2017. *Report on the current open science practice in Serbia and the registry of institutional open science repositories and related information infrastructures*. Project BE-OPEN – Boosting Engagement of Serbian Universities in Open Science). Available from: <http://www.beopen.uns.ac.rs/documents/395d19db7fede71f8ff138cf26d873d4/Report%20on%20the%20existing%20institutional%20open%20science%20repositories%20in%20Serbia.pdf>. Accessed 20 August 2018.
57. Čolović, Petar, and Dejan Pajić. 2017. *Survey on open science attitudes and experiences among Serbian scholars*. Project BE-OPEN – Boosting Engagement of Serbian Universities in Open Science). Available from: <http://www.beopen.uns.ac.rs/documents/35a4f18a51b8b1b54a9dec74afea72a3/Survey%20on%20open%20science%20awareness%20in%20Serbia.pdf>. Accessed 20 August 2018.
58. Ševkušić, Milica, Zorica Janković, and Aleksandra Kužet. 2017. *Open Access Journals in Serbia: Policies and Practices*. Belgrade: National Library of Serbia. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.801673>.
59. New Science Europe Principles on Open Access Publisher Services. 2015. Science Europe. Available from: https://www.scienceeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/270415_Open_Access_New_Principles.pdf. Accessed 20 August 2018.

ANNEX 1: PhD theses in Library and Information Science at the University of Belgrade (2013-2017)

1. Tomić, Nevena (2013) **Biblioteke verskih zajednica i institucija** / Libraries of religious communities and institutions
2. Filić, Milorad (2013) **Srpska književnost na Kosovu i Metohiji : 1852-1941 : bibliografija knjiga i brošura** / The Serbian literature in Kosovo and Metohia : 1852-1941 : bibliography of printed books and pamphlets
3. Mitrović-Marić, Jasmina (2013) **Biblioteka, škola i mediji** / Library, school, media
4. Sabovljević, Dragana (2014) **Bibliografija Todora Manojlovića** / Todor Manojlović – Bibliography
5. Utvić, Miloš (2014) **Izgradnja referentnog korpusa savremenog srpskog jezika** / The construction of reference corpus of contemporary Serbian
6. Brzulović Stanislavljević, Tatjana S. (2015) **Arhivska građa u privatnim zbirkama Univerzitetske biblioteke "Svetozar Marković" u Beogradu: kulturološki, kulturnoistorijski i informaciono-dokumentacioni aspekt** / The archive material in private collections of the University Library "Svetozar Markovic" in Belgrade: cultural, cultural and historical and information and documentation aspect cultural, cultural and historical and information and documentation aspect"
7. Sofronijević, Adam (2015) **Nova paradigma saradnje u bibliotekama** / New paradigm of library collaboration
8. Dragosavac, Branka (2015) **Javne biblioteke u Srbiji od 1901. do 1918. godine** / Public libraries in Serbia from year 1901. to 1918
9. Ivetić, Nataša J. (2015) **Ličnost i delo Steve Čaturila: kulturno-istorijski i bibliološki aspekt** / Personality and work of Stevo Čaturilo: pertaining to the history of culture and bibliographical aspects
10. Roganović, Vladimir P. (2015) **Recepcija nemačke književnosti i kulture u časopisu "Misao": (1919-1937)** / Reception of German literature and culture in the Belgrade literary magazine "Misao": (1919-1937)
11. Vasiljević, Nebojša (2015) **Automatska obrada pravnih tekstova na srpskom jeziku** / Automatic processing of legal text in Serbian language
12. Petrović, Milica L. (2014) **Uticaj interneta na promene u njuz magazinima u Srbiji** / The influence of Internet on changes in the news magazines in Serbia
13. Trivan, Jelena (2013) **Biblioteke i multikulturalnost** / Libraries and Multiculture
14. Milinković, Jelena G. (2016) **Ženska književnost u časopisu Misao (1919-1937)** / Women's literature in magazine Misao The Thought (1919-1937)
15. Dobrilović Dragović, Jelena R. (2016) **Model za izgradnju sistema kvaliteta u specijalnim bibliotekama** / Model for building quality systems in special libraries
16. Golubović, Ana V. (2016) **Bibliografije iz oblasti lingvistike u naučnoj periodici XIX i XX veka** / Linguistic bibliographies in scholarly journals of 19th and 20th century
17. Selihar, Karla K. (2016) **Srpske čitaonice u Vojvodini do 1918. godine** / Serbian reading rooms in Vojvodina until 1918
18. Ristović, Zoran Ž. (2016) **Kumulativni efekti eksploatacije višejezičnih korpusa u nastavi stranih jezika** / Cumulative effects of exploitation of multilingual corpora in second language teaching

19. Trtovac, Aleksandra S. (2016) **Deskriptori metapodataka i deskriptori sadržaja u pronalaženju informacija u digitalnim bibliotekama** / Metadata descriptors and content descriptors for information retrieval in digital libraries
20. Tasić, Radmila (2016) **Omladinska međuratna periodika: studija i bibliografija** / Youth interwar periodical: study and bibliography
21. Gostimirović, Slavica (2016) **Bibliografija časopisa "Razvitak" sa književnoistorijskom studijom** / Bibliography of the journal "Razvitak" with literary and historical study
22. Mišić, Danijela (2014) **Engleski roman za decu i mlade u prevodu na srpski jezik: studija i bibliografija (1972-2011)** / English novel for children and young people translated into Serbian language: study and bibliography (1972-2011)
23. Arbutina, Nada (2016) **Legat u biblioteci** / Legacy in a library
24. Vučenović, Tamara S. (2016) **Biblioteka kao nosilac participativnih praksi u kulturi u kontekstu informacionog društva** / Library as the bearer of the participatory practices in culture in the context of information society
25. Martinović, Milena (2016) **Rukopisne knjige manastira Rođenje presvete Bogorodice na Cetinju** / The manuscript books at the monastery of The nativity of blessed Virgin Mary in Cetinje
26. Jaćimović, Jelena B. (2016) **Automatsko prepoznavanje i normalizacija vremenskih izraza u nestrukturiranim novinskim i medicinskim tekstovima na srpskom jeziku** / Automatic recognition and normalization of temporal expressions in Serbian unstructured newspaper and medical texts
27. Idrizović, Nenad (2016) **Patrijaršijska biblioteka Srpske pravoslavne crkve 1706-2006** / The Patriarchal Library, Sremski Karlovci, The Metropolitanate of Karlovci, reading-rooms, The Serbian Orthodox Church, Serbian librarianship, Belgrade